

Smart Fog-Hub Service in airport (SFHS): A fog-to-cloud based proximity marketing and topics adviser system for travellers

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Foreword

The managed Fog-to-Cloud (mF2C) Project has been funded by the EU Horizon2020 Programme. It has designed and developed a hierarchical and decentralized management architecture for a fog-to-cloud scenario, which is intended to be secure, robust, scalable and efficient. The resulting solution is based on a software agent to be deployed on all computing elements participating to the mF2C system, from cloud to the IoT devices at the edge.

Three different use cases have been developed to validate the mF2C architecture. This article describes the third use case, which has been conceived in a typical smart city context such as the Elmas Airport in Cagliari, Italy. The pilot leverages the use of the mF2C technology to setup hubs in the airport capable of tracking the presence of people and other objects, in order to provide value added services on top for proximity marketing, prediction of path/behaviour of consumers, and taking real time decisions. The app provides assistance to all travellers, but is particularly valuable for elderly or disabled people, with potential extensions for emergency situations. It gives chance to travellers to discover all facilities of the airport, aided by a recommender system using machine learning, which can make suggestions according with travellers' preferences or on similarities to other travellers.

The final validation in the real-world scenario has given evidence that the adoption of the fog-to-cloud approach brings relevant benefits in terms of performance and optimization of resource usage, thus demonstrating the efficacy of the mF2C technology.

More details on the mF2C framework, addressed research, technical and implementation challenges can be found in the documents referenced at the end of this article.

Keywords: Cloud computing, fog computing, fog-to-cloud, distributed systems, IoT, machine learning, people tracking, proximity marketing

1. Introduction

Air transportation is one of the most important modes of transport, and the number of passengers is constantly increasing, with a significant number of novice passengers. The airport structures are increasingly extended, offering an ever-greater number of services. For both novice and experienced travellers, the experience of moving through large airports to reach the right gate at the right time can be a stressful part of their travel. Monitors, indications, and announcements aim at facilitating all operations, but moving in crowded and noisy places implies some form of stress when visiting airports. For this reason, the emerging idea is to identify an indoor navigator and recommender solution that could provide travellers a more enjoyable and stress-free experience. First of all, this solution would integrate all information that airports already provide through all digital monitors, information kiosks and voice announcement. Secondly, the entire airport map and list of available services with associated Points of Interest (POI), such as restrooms, shops, duty-free areas, information desks, gates should be included. This kind of solution aims at fulfilling the wish for a user-friendly and interactive indoor map offering passengers an easy way to get to preferred shops and other points of interest. Instead of spending time finding their gate and waiting nearby because of the fear of missing their flight, travellers could explore the overall offering of shops, restaurants, and services in their waiting time. This would result in excellent customer experience, but at the same time in an opportunity to increase revenue for the airport and service providers. This would be a win-win scenario.

Such a recommendation system needs to be designed as a kind of end-user interaction widely used in e-commerce (Amazon), social network websites (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter), streaming portals (YouTube, Netflix) or Large Retail sites.

Recommender engines try to infer tastes and preferences for a user based on his or her past actions and similarities to

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other users. In addition, recommender engines try to identify unknown items that might be of interest to users. People’s tastes generally follow patterns. For instance, people usually tend to like things that are similar to other things they like, and they usually tend to like things that similar people like. Recommendation algorithms use these patterns to predict likes and dislikes. It is possible to generate recommendations based on either users or items.

The most commonly used and effective technique for recommender systems is Collaborative Filtering. It is widely used across social media, retail, and streaming services, and is based on the behaviour of users, and the idea that people that share an interest in certain things will probably have similar tastes in other things as well. The collaborative filtering recommender engine does not need to know details about the properties for each item to produce a recommendation. In our scenario, people that own a smartphone or other connected device get tracked and engaged to express their preferences and behaviour.

The overall idea is to track and engage all people and objects in the field and use a Collaborative Filtering based recommender system with machine learning algorithms to get the best possible customer experience, with suggestion on the best way to use available services, e.g. suggest to move close to the gate or notify the final call or recommend relevant proposals and offerings in shops close to the user. All these suggestions can be refined according to behaviour and choices made by passengers, by means of machine learning based features.

Particular care has been provided for the privacy and security of personal data: the recommender system uses algorithms that operate successfully without any personal information.

The set of IoT devices (smartphones) in the airport field generates a continuous stream of data (position and behaviour) that need to be processed in real-time. These data can generate feedback by way of event notifications (proximity, flight based, etc.) or suggestions based on users’ similarities. At the same time, user behaviour and scoring of different Points of Interest require collaborative filtering (machine learning) tasks. The whole dataflow is represented in the following picture.

Figure 1 - UC3 dataflow between different layers

The use of a recommendation system asks for massive data processing that grows with the number of managed objects. Even a smaller airport like Cagliari Elmas manages about 4 million passengers per year, so a relevant part of them (and their related behaviour tracking) will feed the machine learning algorithms.

Thus, there is a need to scale capabilities in order to balance huge amount of processing from fog to cloud nodes and manage distributed data. The mF2C technology offers all requested features to orchestrate and distribute the processing with automated scaling when needed.

The continuous tracking of people moving in the airport could allow for the discovery of bottlenecks in airport services or suggestions to improve available resources. At the same time, all dealers and service providers in the airport site will benefit from the application in their marketing proposals and offering by using the anonymized data collected by all people in the field. For these reasons, the recommendation system can facilitate the win-win goal (travelers experience, shoppers’ revenues, suggestions for airport planners).

1.1. Document layout

This document describes the deployment of the final proof-of-concept of the mF2C architecture in the context of the real-world use case in the airport. In the following chapters the final design and implementation of the mF2C architecture will be presented, then the specific deployment of the UC3 in the real-world environment, the used testbeds, the specific hardware and software settings, the data flow diagrams, the experimentation set-ups and the results obtained together with numerical KPI. Finally, conclusions reached during the work, business considerations and potential follow-ups will be shaped.

2. mF2C final architecture

2.1. main concepts

The mF2C system proposes a coordinated management solution for all resources, from the edge to the cloud, with a view of optimizing services execution. The proposed solution leverages a hierarchical and decentralized architecture whose main component is referred to as the Agent. The Agent is deployed on different elements participating in the overall mF2C system, which includes the complete set of functionalities considered within the management framework. In short, the mF2C management solution is a software suite to be deployed on the different devices willing to participate in mF2C. From an architectural perspective, the set of mF2C devices are distributed to different layers, setting a hierarchical management architecture where several nodes acting as leaders (or cluster heads), are responsible for managing the nodes behind in a scalable way. Figure 2 shows the envisioned layered architecture for mF2C, illustrating the different agents in a hierarchical structure and potential IoT devices directly attached to the agents.

Figure 2 - mF2C layered architecture

From a functional perspective the Agent instantiates the set of functionalities the mF2C management framework is expected to provide. Functionalities are split into two main functional components, the **Agent Controller (AC)** and the **Platform Manager (PM)**, as shown in Figure 3. The PM provides the high-level functionalities, responsible for inter-agent communications (agents communicate through their PMs) and has the capacity to take decisions with a more global view. On the other hand, the Agent Controller (AC) functionalities have a more local scope, dealing with local resources and services.

Figure 3 - mF2C IT-2 Agent architecture

As shown in Figure 3, the AC and the PM include several internal components to support both interoperability and to provide global functionality.

Indeed, the Figure shows the main building blocks that compose the agent entity: Platform Manager (PM), Agent Controller (AC), dataClay as a data management related component, Security block comprised of Control Area Unit (CAU) Client, Reverse Proxy and AC library providing an agent with standard functionalities like cryptography, etc., an Event Manager, GUI and an API as an entry point [1, 2, 3, 8, 9, 10].

3. The use case: Smart Fog-Hub Service (SFHS)

3.1. final architecture

The following diagram represents the final architecture of the Smart Fog Hub Service Use Case.

Figure 1 UC3 final system architecture

This platform aims to allow the end user a friendly and interactive experience during the stay and moving in the airport field, using an Android app specifically designed and developed for this purpose [4, 5, 6].

The main functionalities are:

- 1) Proximity computation of POI and notification delivery to the user. The notification can include a brief message, for example a promotion or discount for a shop, or other useful information. The proximity range is defined for each single POI, thus allowing end user notifications even for relative long distances in the coverage area. The possibility to configure this range could fulfil specific business-driven requirements for service providers. For example, it could be used by a shop that wants to reach the largest possible audience for its advertisement, even in a given time slot.
- 2) Subscription for notifications on the traveller flight. The traveller can choose in the app his/her flight and be notified for status changes, like departure time, gate assignment or change, delay, etc. The information about the flights are taken from the external information systems of the airport.
- 3) Subscription for notifications on specific topics of interest to the user. This feature could be particularly useful for notifying the user of information or events of interest are outside the airport, in places that the user wishes to reach or visit. For example, the user can be notified about the status of city transports, folklore events, movies programming at the cinema etc.

- 4) Rating tool for the POI. Through the app, the end user can see the information for a given POI and vote his/her feedback (a simple score from 1 to 5 stars). Currently it is not possible for the end user to post a comment, but this feature can be developed in the future enabling a proper user identification.
- 5) Topics Advisor fed by historical end user ratings. This feature, based on Machine Learning algorithms, provides a list of suggested POIs that could be of interest to the user.
- 6) Administrative dashboard for system and user behaviour monitoring. It includes more tools and minor improvements. This software, developed for demo purposes, can be further improved taking into consideration business-oriented suggestions provided by the service providers.

All listed features have been implemented throughout the project duration and demonstrated in the final deployment. All software is deployed as docker containers to improve development, operations and maintenance, achieving a high level of reliability and stability.

The UI of the Android app has been totally redesigned and improved, offering a better and smooth end user experience.

Figure 2 UC3 security architecture

Particular care has been taken to the security aspects of the whole platform, both in the architecture and in the developed software, thus a custom PKI is used to fully support them. All communications between different software components use certificates signed by a custom root CA, so communications are tamper-proof. In particular, the communication between Android app and the API server uses both client and server certificates for mutual recognizing. Moreover, the Android app uses a JWT (JSON web token) to identify and recognize the device session and to access the API server functionalities [7].

3.1.1. Current hardware and base software

The hardware and software in the final deployment aims to fully support the functionalities described above, offering suitable performance, stability and reliability.

The devices that compose the platform architecture, depicted in Table 4, are:

- A set of RaspberryPi, which act as wi-fi access point for the end user smartphones with the specific Android app installed. A single RaspberryPi hosts the https REST API server that provides all the functionalities needed by the Android app; moreover, it keeps trace in a local database the end user device sessions together with other needed data. In this way, each RaspberryPi handles its own cluster of end user devices. All end user data collected are synchronized with the backend software in order to make them available to the upper layer on the software stack. The software handles automatically the handover in case that the end user device switches between different platform access points.

- A SixSq Nuvlabox mini, which hosts the backend software which collects in a local database all data coming from the lower software stack, which basically are end user session data. This database is the main point of view of all user data collected in real time in the field and is accessed by the administration dashboard; moreover, it stores and handles all information needed for proper end user notification, e.g. flight status changes, advertisement for shops, topics related messages, etc. This set of information is properly delivered to the lower layer of the software in order to make them available to the end users in their devices. Furthermore, this device hosts another software component, which is in charge to query the airport API that provides real time flights status data and store them in the local database.
- A set of miniPC x86 devices, which host the mF2C agent and services in the fog layer.
- A cloud VM in an OpenStack instance, hosted and managed by ENG, which hosts mF2C cloud agent and service, and another software component in charge to store the anonymized historical end user data useful for long term statistics, in a local database.

The following table lists all devices and installed software:

Edge IoT devices	
Smartphone used by end-users	
Hardware	Software
ASUS ZENFONE 4 MAX CPU: Qualcomm® Snapdragon™ 430 Mobile Platform with 64-bit Octa-core Processor GPU: Qualcomm® Adreno™ 505 (SD430) Memory: LPDDR3 3GB Internal storage: eMCP 32GB Display: 5.5-inch IPS Main Rear Camera 13 Mpix, Front Camera 8 Mpix Wireless Technology: WLAN 802.11 b/g/n; Bluetooth 4.1; Wi-Fi direct Sensor : Front fingerprint sensor, Accelerator, E-Compass, Gyroscope, Proximity sensor, Ambient light Navigation : GPS, AGPS, GLO, BDS	Operating system: Android Nougat (v7) Custom app for user engagement
RaspberryPi3 Model B 1.2	
Hardware	Software
Broadcom BCM2837 SoC, with quad-core ARM Cortex-A53 1200 MHz processor VideoCore IV dual-core 400 MHz GPU 1 GB SDRAM - shared by the GPU and CPU MicroSD card slot for boot and storage 4 x USB 2.0 ports (via on-board 5 port hub) RJ45 10/100 MBit/s Ethernet port HDMI and Composite video, CSI (camera) and DSI (display) connectors	Operating System: Raspbian Jessie Lite Docker, version 18.03.0-ce Container A: MongoDB v3.2.18 32bit Container B: API server for end-user session management, based on Node.js v9.10.1 and several npm modules: Express, Mongoose, Socket.io, etc.
L2 Fog-capable devices	
HP Laptop	
Hardware	Software
ibm thinkpad t420i model 4236G90 intel i3-2350m cpu 2.30GHz 4G ram + 4G swap space 160G HD	Ubuntu 18.04 - CentOS 7.4 mF2C agent, mF2C service application
L1 Fog-capable devices	
Nuvlabox Mini	
Hardware	Software

Intel Celeron processor 8 GB RAM 128 GB SSD 60 W external power supply WiFi 2 USB 2.0; 2 USB 3.0 VGA / HDMI 2 x RJ-45 network interface	Centos 7.1 CloudLayer: OpenNebula Virtualization: Kvm AppStore: SlipStream CentOS Linux release 7.4.1708 (Core) Docker 18.03.1-ce - Docker Compose 1.21.2 Container A: MongoDB v3.6.0 Container B: Backend server based on Node.js v8.9.2, and several npm modules: Express, Mongoose, Socket.io, etc.
L0 Cloud-capable devices	
Cloud Virtual Machine	
(Virtual) Hardware	Software
VM with 2 vCpu, 16G RAM 100G storage	Centos 7.4 MF2C Agent Application for data collection

Table 1. Current hardware and base software in UC3

3.1.2. Software responsibilities

The full stack of software components in the use case consists of eight modules. New features and optimizations have been added in the final period. The following list describes the components and the functionalities.

- API server (with SSL), hosted in the RaspberryPi.
 1. Provides API endpoints for the Android app installed on user devices
 2. Forwards device/user position data to the mF2C service, which is used for real-time proximity computation
 3. Stores user session data in the local database and forward them to the upper layer backend module (the fog backend module), in order to synchronize data between databases. This synchronization is performed by specific tasks, which runs periodically at configured interval time.
 4. Receives notifications messages from the upper layer backend module and make them available to end users' devices by using proper API endpoints. These notifications messages can be related to POI or specific topics or can be an update of the status of the traveller's flight.
- Fog Backend module, hosted in Nuvlabox mini
 1. Receives device position and other user session data from the lower layer API server through synchronization tasks and stores them in the local database. Thus, this database contains all the sessions data provided by all the user devices in the field, each one connected to its own access point.
 2. Stores the updates for the flight status in the local database, supplied by another specific module, and forwards them to the lower layer API server through specific synchronization tasks, which runs periodically at configured interval time.
 3. Stores notification messages related to POI and topics in the local database and forwards them to the lower layer API server through specific synchronization tasks, which runs periodically at configured interval time.
 4. Stores statistics data like user movement tracking in the local database, making them available to the Administration Dashboard module. These data are forwarded to the upper Cloud backend module for long-term storage and analysis, through specific synchronization tasks.
- Flights status update module, hosted in Nuvlabox mini
 1. Query the airport API for real time flight status
 2. Updates the status of the flights stored in the local database. The database is the same used by the fog backend module.
- Administration dashboard, hosted in Nuvlabox mini
 1. Get data to analyze and display from the local database. The database is the same used by the fog backend module
 2. Provides a web GUI for system administrators and field operators
- Cloud backend module, hosted in the cloud VM instance
 1. Provides long-term storage for users' sessions and other useful historical data ready for statistics. All stored data come from the lower fog layer and are properly anonymized for privacy compliance.
- Topics Advisor, hosted in the cloud VM instance as mF2C service
 1. Provides the engine for Collaborative Filtering algorithm used for end user recommendations for POI. The data used for computation are taken from the local database. This engine runs periodically in batch mode, the timing can be configured as needed by the system administrators according to the volume of data produced in the field.

2. Stores the result in the local database, available for the lower layers and ready to be queried on-demand by the end user Android app.
- mF2C agent and services, hosted in miniPC and cloud VM instance
 1. Provide the deploy of mF2C related software components
 2. Provide the software stack for specific functionalities detailed above.
 - Android app, installed on end user devices.
 1. Provides the UI and all functionalities for the end user, connecting with the API server.

Figure 3 Privacy Architectural hardware and software components

As shown in figure 6, the data layer in the platform consists of several local databases instances, which are synchronized both ways, between the upper (backends hosted in Nuvlabox and Cloud) and lower (edge/API server in the RaspberryPi). This approach assures the delivery of the data when and where needed, and emphasizes the data proximity concept. All databases are instances of MongoDB.

As described in other deliverables, the mF2C agent uses internally dataClay for its data communications and sharing.

3.1.3. Tasks to be executed by the mF2C Agent

In this use case, there are two main tasks deployed as mF2C services, and thus managed by the agent, as described below:

- Proximity computation, given the end user position in the field. Each position update is generated by the end user movement in the field, sent to the API server and stored in the local database. The position is then compared with the list of POI in the field and the computation result is the list of nearby POIs. Nearby means, as mentioned before, that the user is located inside the “coverage area” of the specific POI, and this can be configured individually for each POI according with business strategies. For example, the service provider can offer a pricing option for larger coverage areas, giving the POI’s owner the chance to promote it to a larger audience.
- Recommendation of Points of Interest (POI). This task uses Machine Learning algorithm (Collaborative Filtering) to propose a custom list for each user, containing the POI that similar users like most. The concept of similarity is

based on previous user preferences and feedback for the POI, thus if a user has not yet given any feedback, the system propose the plain list of the most preferred POI by all the users, considering the whole dataset of ratings.

The adoption of the mF2C system gives two main benefits. First, it is possible to handle both up and down scaling, according to the number of simultaneous users to manage. When the number of users grows, the system administrators can easily put in place additional devices in the fog layer, install the mF2C agent and deploy services in them, in order to support efficiently the larger load in processing data. At the opposite, if the number of users decreases, the system administrators can decide to dismiss some resources, simply by stopping services and/or get out devices.

In this use case scenario, the number of users can be easily gotten by airport statistics but also by analysing user tracking long-term data stored in the cloud layer of the platform.

Another clear benefit of the mF2C system is that it is able to manage more than one fog areas in more complex scenarios like smart cities (e.g. a fog area in the airport, another in the train station, another in specific tourist places of interest in the city, etc.). Doing this it is possible to develop and offer a complex set of services to end users who subscribes to the system. These services could be free or paid, even managed by different service providers, but finally handled by mF2C services. Moreover, being mF2C agent able to proper manage resources and services in the whole set of available devices, they can be used effectively and optimized for service execution.

This could and should be done taking into account the privacy of the user data, which is always a strict requirement, by leveraging built-in mF2C security features.

3.2. Use Case storyline

The user experience starts when the traveller completes the security check and reach the departure pier with all gates. He/she follow the instructions and download and install the airport app in his/her Android smartphone.

Once the app has been started the first mandatory step is related to reading and accepting the privacy terms, in this case the shown information explains that no personal or personal identifiable information will be used nor stored by the app.

Figure 4 Privacy Terms and first configuration on the app

After that, the user can configure the app according to the following:

- his/her own flight, to get informed on important events related to the flight (assign gate, change gate, delays, first call, last call); In case he/she can change later the selected flight.
- topics of interest, in order to be informed of available Points of Interest (PoIs) in the area.

Then the user moves freely in the field, being tracked and notified about POI's proximity. By the app in every moment the user can get all available information on the selected flight, flight status, and so on.

Figure 5 main information available in tabs

Moreover, the app has the following tabs:

- Places
- Recommendations
- Notifications
- Favourites
- Map

Selecting Places, the user can proactively search interesting PoIs, with possibility to get more information on offered services. In this way he/she can realize the whole amount of services offered and make his own choices. But he/she can move around getting driven by PoIs discovery.

Selecting Recommendations, the user can get recommendations on interesting PoIs according to the selected topics and check the rate of the listed PoIs. The option of rating PoIs feeds the topics advisor system, based on Collaborative Filtering algorithm, that propose some PoIs to the user according to the similarities in behaviour with other users.

The Notifications tab shows all relevant alerts on the flight status, nearby PoIs and favorite topics, so here the user is advised to check this periodically. A red bullet announces the reception of new notifications.

The Favorites tab shows the most rated PoIs, so here the user can be driven by the rating of other users. Here he can find daily promotions offered by the various shops.

Finally, the Map tab shows the position of the user in the field as he/she moves, with different symbols to represent the user and available PoIs.

Figure 9 more details on PoIs and the map

There is another usage, dedicated to the airport administrators. They can connect to the [Admin Portal](#), get access to a unified view of the field, having the ability to manage the PoIs information, and related promotions, but also the real time information on active users, with possibility to have dedicated reporting. These reports can show the behaviour of travellers, offering way of co-hort analysis, splitting the users according to low-cost or business flights, or destination or other fields. All these reports can spot bottlenecks in the airport infrastructure and suggest ways of improving it.

3.2.1. Business improvements

The Smart Fog Hub System in airport application has been conceived from scratch, starting from the idea to track and engage all people and objects in the field and use a topics advisor based on machine learning algorithms to get the best possible customer experience, with suggestion on the best way to use available services, and modelling the proximity and advisor services according to the fog-to-cloud paradigm. While in iteration one of the project the focus was on technical development of the base components of the application, in iteration two the following business improvements were introduced:

- **Support of proximity marketing in a real scenario:** the huge amount of travellers that install and use the Android app requires the intelligent distribution of processing on all available nodes, with automatic scaling when needed, satisfying the real time constraints demanded by the application. This improvement has been achieved by the use of the mF2C orchestration feature that enable to setup a SLA policy on response time that will be enforced at runtime, and the COMPSs capabilities to distribute and balance automatically the processing between all available nodes;
- **Deploy of the Topics advisor:** the use of the Topics advisor offers travellers way to receive recommendations based on user's similarities. Since this algorithm is fed by preferences and behaviour of users, the amount of processing increase with the number of registered users, thus the need to leverage the mF2C capabilities to shift the processing from fog to cloud;
- **Real-time flight information embedded in the app:** the solution developed in iteration two integrates all information that the airport already provides through all digital monitors, information kiosks and voice announcements, customized on the specific traveller's needs. This has been a consequence of the mF2C platform functionalities and technical/business improvements developed by the use case provider;
- **Security and Privacy support:** since the mF2C agent is not supported yet on the Android smartphones, the built-in security and privacy capabilities offered by the mF2C platforms have been extended with a custom PKI to guarantee the same level of security until the end-devices at the edge. As a result, the application offers full security and privacy functionalities fulfilling the GDPR and security requirements, guaranteeing full acceptance by the users. This improvement results from exploiting the embedded mF2C functionalities and extensions made by the use case provider;

- **Fog computation:** The shift of processing on the fog, with offloading only in case of need offers a better control on managed data. The Fog Hub in the airport is the main collector of real time processing, minimizing the use of cloud, thus improves data locality and contributes to the overall security and privacy, since only the long term archiving and massive computations are performed in the cloud. The mF2C approach here decreases the amount of transferred data to the cloud and the amount of computation in the cloud, lowering the overall cost of the application;
- **Application portal for POIs and data management:** the deployment of the application portal enables the management of all information at fog level, from the perspective of the airport planners. It includes a set of reports and graphical diagrams on user's behaviour and movements that could allow for the discovery of bottlenecks in airport services or suggestions to improve available resources. The mF2C enables a reduction in the volume of transferred data as most of the data to be managed is stored in fog nodes.

The business improvements described above, with the native mF2C capabilities, offer a relevant set of functionalities to adapt the Smart Fog Hub in other smart-city scenarios, even combining different fogs located in near sites, like train, metro stations or shopping centres, interacting, sharing customer behaviour data gathered to improve the effectiveness of marketing proposals, given that the identity of objects/customers is protected.

3.2.2. Technical improvements

In the second phase of the project, several improvements have been made to leverage the full potential of the fog-to-cloud approach and enriching the functionalities and maturity of the use case, starting from what has been developed in the first phase. The following list summarizes these improvements.

- Implementation of the ML based Topics advisor as a new mF2C service, hosted on a cloud node, so the Android app can suggest some PoIs according to "user's similarity";
- Evolution of the mF2C proximity service with better capability to spread computation tasks across different nodes, leveraging the fog-to-cloud approach;
- Full adoption of a custom PKI for secure communications between all components, including those occurring between the Android app and backend APIs in the fog nodes;
- UI/UX improvements of the Android app, consisting of a complete redesign of the screens and navigation, to be more appealing and to achieve better usability and stability;
- Backend APIs enhancement, with an improvement in the data model, for a full support of the Android app;
- Integration to the real-time flight system information of the Cagliari airport for the continuous dispatching of relevant flight information to interested travellers;
- Enhancement of the Admin Portal, including new statistical graphs for PoIs visiting and topics of interest chosen by users, to give airport administrators a complete view of the airport infrastructure usage, with chance to spot bottlenecks or possible improvements.
- The Use Case has been modified to be configured and launched from the mF2C service catalogue. For this a specific SLA template, with a performance policy, needs to be created. The performance policy is related to the real-time constraint demanded by the airport use case and is enforced at runtime.

3.3. Data Flow Diagrams

In addition to the functionalities already present in the first version, some new functionalities and integrations have been developed specifically for the final release. The workflows are detailed in the following paragraphs.

3.3.1. App functionalities

The UI of the Android app has been continuously improved, collecting feedbacks and suggestions, for a better user experience. The following are the latest functionalities added.

- Rating for a specific POI. The user can select a specific POI and assign a rating from 1 to 5 stars. The rating, properly anonymized, is then delivered in the system until the Cloud backend, where is stored and made available to the topics advisor engine for further computation.
- List of recommended POI. The user can see on-demand the list of recommended POI, which is based on similar user's ratings and is tailored for him/her. This list is produced by the recommended engine.

The workflow for these functionalities is detailed in paragraph **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**. As already stated, the app needs to connect to the API Server to provide all the functionalities.

3.3.2. User tracking with proximity notification

Figure 6 Sequence diagram of user tracking with proximity notification

The figure 10 shows the process for the user that moves in the field while using the Android app. In this scenario, the position data is computed in the user device, which is the smartphone in the diagram, sent to the API Server and stored. This data is then used to compute nearby POI, involving the specific mF2C service. If there are messages related to the found POI, they are finally sent to the user device for proper notification and displaying.

3.3.3. Flight updates and favorite topics notification

Figure 7 Sequence diagram of flight update

The figure 11 shows the process for the flight update. In this scenario, the end user, typically a traveller, choose his/her flight from the airport timetable. The list is provided by querying an external real-time API hosted in the airport systems and filtered in order to provide only departure flights that a traveller can take. So, for example, departed flights are filtered out from the list. The real-time updates for all the flights are stored in the Fog backend and synchronized in the API Server, where are made available for proper notification to the user. Periodically, in a short time interval, the Android app requests information about the status of the flight chosen by the user. If there are updates, the app promptly notifies the user. Considered updates are, for example, changes regarding the gate, departure time, status like delayed, last call, boarding, etc.

Figure 8 Sequence diagram for favorite topics notification

The figure 12 shows the workflow related to the user’s favourite topics notification. The user can select one or more topics of his/her interest from a list, which is configured in a specific catalogue in the API Server database. The topics selected by the user are sent to the API Server and stored in its local database. Holding this data, the system is able to deliver to the user proper notification messages.

The Fog backend has in its local database the complete dataset of the information about topics. For example, this data set can be loaded in with batch jobs or even supplied time by time by mean of the administrator dashboard. The dataset is finally synchronized to the API Server, so when the app periodically requests for updates on the topics selected by the user, the API Server returns them, and the app display the notification messages.

3.3.4. Recommendations

Figure 9 Sequence diagram of topics advisory process

The figure 13 shows the process for the recommendation's functionality. In this process, each user can provide a rating for specific POI. All user ratings for all POI are then sent and stored in the Cloud backend database. This dataset is used by the so-called topics advisor engine to compute recommendations for individual users, using a Machine Learning algorithm. The topics advisor engine is an mF2C service that periodically performs this sort of computation. The output of computation is then sent to the Cloud backend database for storage. When the end user demands the list of recommended POI, the request is forwarded to the Cloud backend database that returns the list for that individual user. Finally, this list is notified to the user in the Android app.

3.3.5. Admin portal

Figure 10 Sequence diagram for dashboard web application

The figure 14 shows the data flow for the Admin Portal (Web Dashboard) component. The system operator accesses to the Admin Portal with a browser and uses all provided functionalities. The data are taken from either the Fog backend or the Cloud backend, depending on the functionality used.

3.4. Experimental set up

In order to test proficiently the Smart Fog Hub, UC3 of the mF2C project, we improved first our internal testbed with more resources at fog level, enabling us to test the load balancing under different conditions, using more fog nodes and the cloud to get better results. Several runs have been done to validate the capability of the mF2C agent to distribute the services on all available computing resources, guaranteeing optimal response times.

In this scenario this is the list of devices used for the extensive tests:

- Some Smartphone (ASUS, Samsung) have been used to run the airport app,
- 4 RaspberryPI3 have been used to track people in the field and provide the available services,
- 3 miniPC with 8GB of RAM have been used as fog nodes, that have access to the public airport API (running in voli.sogaer.it server) to get real-time flight information
- Link to the OpenStack instance for cloud support.

With this setup we succeeded in testing the platform under different loading, even simulating more end-users moving in the field, and the different fog and cloud nodes have been attached and detached to check how the system determine the available resources and optimize the scheduling of tasks.

Figure 11 IT-2 internal testbed for Use Case 3

Then the final setting in the airport has been defined. Some meetings with technical specialists of the airport have been held and we decided that the departure pier would be the best option for various reasons:

- Higher concentration of passengers that stay longer in this area
- More shops and PoIs in general
- Easier way to cabling and connecting all devices

In order to guarantee a full coverage of this area 8 points have been selected to install the RaspberryPIs, as in the following picture:

Figure 12 UC3 deployment in the airport

The Blue spots represents the points where we placed the RaspberryPI3, while the green and red spots present existing airport WIFI AP that can be used as additional points to improve the precision of people tracking.

The fog nodes have been positioned in a separate datacentre room, with the router that is fibre connected with the Tiscali Datacentre, which guarantee connection with the Openstack instance.

All computing nodes work in a dedicated VLAN, so separated from the airport equipment, thus fulfilling a security strict requirement imposed by the airport.

The list of devices used for the final scenario and demonstration is the following:

- More Smartphones to run the airport app, and in the testbed several runs have been performed with high number of simulated users,
- 8 RaspberryPI3, as described in Figure 13, to guarantee full coverage of the departure area, to track people in the field and provide the available services,
- 3 miniPC with 8GB of RAM have been used as fog (working) nodes,
- 1 Nuvlabox mini equipped with 8 GB RAM, that acts as fog leader, provides real-time computing and storage resources to the edge elements, and have access to the public airport API (on voli.sogaer.it server) to get real-time flight information
- CISCO 3400 providing fibre connection to the Tiscali datacentre

- OpenStack instance for cloud support and long-term storage for all data produced that needs to be analysed, even offline, in order to provide feedbacks on system behaviour and allow for possibly optimizations.

Figure 13 UC3 final system diagram

More tests have been performed in the final testbed, in order to validate the use case in the final settings, facing a real-world scenario and related challenges.

This setting could be extended, according with airport requests, adding more RaspberryPis to cover other areas of the airport, and more fog nodes could be added as well to scale-up the system as the number of people to be tracked grows, leveraging the automatic load distribution and off-loading provided by the mF2C agent through COMPSs.

3.5. Results and KPI measurements

Since the focus of the use case is on a fully edge centric solution the defined KPIs resemble the key elements of the Fog/Edge computing paradigm:

Latency and response Time –

The continuous interaction with the user at the edge and the real time response demanded by proximity marketing ask for fast and optimized response time, leveraging the mF2C orchestration, load balancing and distribution, with a proficient use of resources (processing, storage, communication). This is stressed by the huge amount of data (movements, choices, rates, preferences, etc.) that is generated by all end-users. This force the optimal distribution and automatic scalability capabilities of the mF2C framework.

For all these reasons a real time response time for every user under every circumstance is mandatory.

Bandwidth and QoS –

Applications are based on continuous data communication, so tight engagement with the end user, require efficient use of available bandwidth and resilience capabilities.

This is fulfilled by the hierarchical communication structure and redundant architecture elements of the mF2C, that take advantage of the redundant links at the edge and enables the correct functioning of the system even in case of failure of some components.

Data locality and Regulatory Compliance -

Given the high performance of current (and future) edge devices, distributed processing between nearby nodes is more efficient than referring to far-away centralized servers in the cloud. The same edge devices are powerful enough to use intelligent software and run autonomous decision-making applications. Since all data, including personal and sensitive data, is generated and located in the edge, fast calculation is possible locally without the need to move data to the cloud,

where fog-to-cloud topology enable filtering and optimization on resources & communications while fulfilling the real-time requirement, not possible with direct cloud topology.

The control of trust and management of sensitive information need to be started from the edge, from people that use these devices.

With these assumption privacy and security by design are implemented in the mF2C framework, thus guaranteeing the confidentiality, integrity and availability of personal data, fulfilling GDPR rules.

Applications can use these native capabilities and policies enforcement to have satisfactory privacy management.

Performance Tests

To validate the performance of the mF2C within the Use case 3, some following measure has been defined:

- ⊙ **Latency:** measured from the smartphone to fog and cloud devices
- ⊙ **Response Time:** the time measured at the client premises, from the time of the request to the reception of the answer.

A laptop with wi-fi connection has been chosen as the client, and Jmeter has been used to launch batteries of increasing simultaneous client requests per second to the server, corresponding to real world scenarios, collecting data on response time under different loads.

The following tests have been defined:

- ⊙ **Smartphone to Fog** (PCbox)
- ⊙ **Smartphone to Cloud** (OpenStack)
- ⊙ **Smartphone to mF2C** (PCbox & OpenStack)

In terms of metrics the response time for every request is collected, in third scenario the number of requests processed at fog level are summed separately, thus determining the percentage of requests processed at fog level against the total. In the “**Smartphone to mF2C**” test the first run has been run with only one fog available node (PCbox), while in the second run an additional PCbox has been included.

The “**Smartphone to mF2C**” approach performed the best, and performance improved adding more fog nodes. With 10000 samples, we measured an improvement of about 25% compared to the “**Smartphone to Cloud**” approach.

Summarizing the following table shows up the fulfilment of defined KPIs:

KPI	description	result
Response Time	The end user application requires real-time response, end-to-end response time for the proximity calculation is performed under fog only, cloud only and mF2C computing environments	The mF2C environment provides an improvement of at least 15% compared to the cloud only environment
Resiliency	The end user application is based on continuous data communication, intrinsic redundancy of the mF2C architecture guarantees better use of bandwidth and resilience capabilities	At least 3 RPI connect to each device with handover capability to link to the strongest signal in the field, so mF2C guarantees better coverage, resiliency capabilities and better use of bandwidth
Data Locality and Regulatory Compliance	Processing of personal data is done at the edge using security/privacy by design mF2C features, thus fulfilling the GDPR constraints. (compliant or not)	Full GDPR compliancy and control on personal data management

Table 2 UC3 KPI summary

4. Business prospective and conclusions

Engineering has validated the initial idea of the adoption of the mF2C to support proximity marketing applications in indoor spaces seems a very good and beneficial decision, and the mF2C capability to manage different fogs gives a relevant advantage in designing and shaping complex smart cities solutions.

For the final deployment of the system, an engagement with the Cagliari Airport Management company (Sogaer) started at the beginning of the current year, they expressed their interest in the proposal, both asking to extend the coverage of the SFHS Use Case to the full airport area, and asking for sophisticate communication means to inform all passengers of the app inviting them to use it. They are interested in developing the app to approach a full commercial maturity of the solution. This could give them chance to collect information on traveller’s behaviour, service usage, spotting bottlenecks in current infrastructure, so giving advice on the best way of improving the airport service offering and maximizing their revenues.

At the same time Engineering Line Business directors expressed their interest to have a commercial product to be offered

and deployed to other airports. Also, Tiscali expressed their interest in the use case, they offered to support the improvement of the usability of the app, they foresee a good opportunity to leverage the engagement of the airport services to sell more products and services.

The entertainment app offered to end users could be enhanced with a freemium proposition, so more revenues in case of premium users, or could include advertise banners.

Engineering plans also to use mF2C as a standardized platform, to be integrated in their commercial and research platforms, to enable simple provisioning of services in fog cases, particularly in smart cities scenarios. In this kind of scenarios, it is also possible to enable payment methods in the platform, so that the end user can take advantage of promotions or special discounts in the region, feeding the microeconomics. For example, it could be possible to enable payments with credit card or through a personal wallet in the app, or even manage cryptocurrencies or tokens in a blockchain, involving all stakeholders, like commercial and administrative partners.

For this reason, Engineering leverage its extensive relationships with Municipal, Regional and Nation Public Administrations to offer new innovative smart cities services, for example to offer advice and guidance to cruise travellers that stay just one day in the city.

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